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PHILOSOPHY OF PEACE, ITS SEMANTICS AND METAPHORS

The article proposes considering the philosophy of peace in its different representations. This diversity of approaches is regarded on semantics and metaphors for peace. The transformations of Kantian ethics and peace conceptualizations are analyzed and is taking also comparison with the Skovoroda's approach to the foundations of the peaceful life. It is emphasizing that the culture of freedom and rule of law make the culture of peace possible.

Key words: *philosophy of peace, semantics, metaphors for peace, freedom, law, culture, Kantian transformations, Skovoroda's tradition, justice.*

В статті пропонується розгляд філософії миру у її різних репрезентаціях. Ця різноманітність підходів розглядається крізь призму семантик і метафорики миру. Здійснюється порівняння кантівської та сквородинівської традиції філософської концептуалізації миру. Підкреслюється, що культура миру має ґрунтуватись на культурі свободи та верховенстві права.

Ключові слова: *філософія миру, семантики, метафорики миру, свобода, право, культура, кантіанські трансформації, сквородинівська традиція, справедливість.*

The war in Ukraine and its tragic consequences give cause to call your attention to the philosophy of peace and its role both by peacemaking activities and education of peacemaker. In the ideal case everybody might be ready to maintain and to defense the peace as a fundamental condition for good life and happiness and universal value. But the reality is far away from it. The illusion that the war, terrorism or military invasion are the best instruments for solving any conflicts and achieving prosperity has a deep roots in the historical memories of national organized societies. The philosophy of peace regards its own task in giving theoretical and practical orientation for peacemakers and all people strengthening peace.

It must be mentioned that the expression “the philosophy of peace” is only the generic term for many philosophical approaches on peace. Therefore nearly all philosophies of peace try giving answer for the fundamental questions: “What is the peace?” and “How is the peace possible?” The answer on these questions in the Pre-modernity was answered rather negative than positive: as a short period between two wars, what generally was used for relax and mobilization of power to a new war.

The dream of the resourceful society and material prosperity is still associating with the war in the 21st century too. We Ukrainian are also involved in this dramatic process of military struggle for recognition of our independency paying for it with our lives both on the battle fields and residential areas. Turning to the philosophical tradition of peace considering it might be mentioned that already Plato shows the degradation on the both sides of the war participants because their humanity was downshifted to the animal existing. The semantics of peace in the ancient cultures show their origin in mythology. Accordingly to it the dove with olive branch had become meaning of the universal peace symbols connecting heaven and earth, Observing the eclipse reason in the battles ancient philosophers have made a very important conclusion about the role of rules, moral and above all law. This intuitions became the further development by Aristotle and St. Thomas Aquinas. His principles of the peaceful social life (personality, solidarity and subsidiarity) in their further transformations were taking as corner stones for EU. Thereby the dividing the people into forces of Good and forces of Evil opens the possibilities for reviving of war ideas. As a pedagogical example for this tendency can be named the Children's Crusade which have taking place in 12-th century and many other confessional wars.

The real revolution in the peace conceptualization was done in the New Time and Enlightenment philosophy. Thomas Hobbs had made a very important step for the later secular conceptualizations of peace. His consideration of peace is a part of the theory of the social contract, which had brought to Hobbes recognition. The peace and free will, so Hobbes, are possible only in the frame of the social contract necessary for balance between liberty and safety [see Jaede, 2018: pp. 43-44, 72-73]. Peace in its secular versions is no more a gift of God's but only human's decision. Since Hobbes the semantics of peace were replaced into social and political fields. The consequence of this replacing was a widening of the senses volume in the peace concept. There was an offensive character given including the possibility of the resistance against the oppressive laws (J.J. Rousseau). Those discrepancies had a hidden danger to be transformed into contradictions with the just war perspective. It was showed convictive in Kant's essay "Perpetual peace". From the standpoint of the whole mankind he had developed his own conception of the steady peace but not as a reality but only as two possibilities with corresponding semantics: an eternal peace – this term is in the original title of this work is : "Zum ewigen Frieden" – and the perpetual peace. The English translation has nothing to do with the semantics distinctions and is only the expression of different epistemic cultures: German transcendentalism and British empiricism have some discrepancies in terminology but in spite of it always stimulate each other with the accent on the idea of the tolerance. The Empiricism concentrates on empirical realities and the transcendentalism – on possibilities searching for ways carrying to perfection of the mankind. Kant's metaphor for eternal peace is the graveyard. The silence and tranquility of cemetery might show the peace in its negation of human being. But this is a dead peace which has nothing to do with the perfection of mankind.

The fulfillment of this project depends on morality embedded in reason. From this instance the categorical imperative should be addressed to all people as the universal law with the absolute validly. Kant calls to treat humanity always as an end goal and never as only means. Therefore one's will maxim ought always to be

articulated as universal Law [Kant,1998: p.51]. The semantics of reason and reasoning have played in further an decisive role in the contemporary peace theories basing on the post-conventional moral reasoning (L. Kohlberg) and Hegel's dialectical considering of the relationship between the war and peace. A New look on the old ideas of reification and struggle for recognition (A.Honneth) and discourse ethics (K.-O. Apel) have signed a communicative turn in the philosophy of peace enriching it with the semantics of co-responsibility, ideal communicating community and those ones of the post-conventional patriotism and cosmopolitism in Kant's spirit. The principle of non-violence is guiding today in social and political life. Only the intolerance against tolerance is unacceptable in Europe. The hymn of EU on the text of Friedrich Schiller's "Ode to Joy" gives a metaphorical explanation to innovative senses of peace communication in the Late Enlightenment. The key phrases of this hymn (translation of Trace Smith, 1972) are following: "all people became brothers", "all creation drink of Joy", "Be embraced, Millions!", "This kiss to all the world".

The idea of tolerance was raised during the Late Modernity to the European universality in its multicultural space constituted by migrants streams. The tolerance as the moral attitude was always typically for the everyday life in Ukraine and for its political relations. The tradition of philosophizing on peace in Ukraine was developed on ideas of Hryhorii Skovoroda (1722-1794)? The contemporary of Kant. In distinction of Kant his peace philosophy is based on irrational assumptions which show some similarity with Schiller's semantics of the peace as joy and nature. The peace is for him an attitude of heart and has an existential intentionality what comes to expression in semantics of freedom, labour and Christian ethics with its virtues. Therefore Skovoroda was a great provider of European philosophical culture in his motherland's space. The semantics of peace in spite of diametric opposite position to Kant show here the tendency of nearing to Kantian problems of moral duties for happy and peaceful life. The escapism of Skovoroda is compensated with his practical advises dealing with the education at home and aboard. His argumentation touching organization of social life on the principle of anthropological and social justice also becomes actuality in the social, cultural and political contexts of the post-industrialism with its technological possibilities using for hybrid wars.

One of more convictive metaphors in Skovoroda's tradition is the family living in peace and accordance with God and nature. The symbols for peace could be after Skovoroda not only doves with the olive branch, but also the larks and the cranes. The symbolic origami paper crane as remembering on Hiroshima tragedy shows also the resonance potential of Skovoroda's peace symbols. The branch of viburnum with the bunch of red fruits might be also regarded as a metaphor for peace. But the most convictive semantics of peace are hidden in the state banner of Ukraine with its blue and yellow colors and will for peace and victory. We, people staying in Kharkov on the borders of the war, are keeping our flag flaying as a peace symbol.

The culture of peace in its positive meaning must be based on the culture of freedom which makes possible to replace the rule of weapon by the rule of the law and ethics of co-responsibility.

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